

18-22 SEPTEMBER 2023

ASSESSING ORGANIC AMENDMENT'S ABILITY TO REDUCE BIOAVAILABILITY OF TRIFLURALIN

Jelena Beljin¹, Marijana Kragulj Isakovski¹, Nina Đukanović¹, Jelena Molnar Jazić¹, Tamara Apostolović¹, Srđan Rončević¹, Snežana Maletić¹

¹ University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Department of Chemistry, Biochemistry and Environmental Protection, Trg Dositeja Obradovica 3, 21000, Novi Sad, Serbia

Corresponding author's full address, phone, and e-mail: University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Department of Chemistry, Biochemistry and Environmental Protection, Trg Dositeja Obradovica 3, 21000, Novi Sad, Serbia
+381604991990, jelena.beljin@dh.uns.ac.rs

all other authors: marijana.kragulj@dh.uns.ac.rs; nina.djukanovic@dh.uns.ac.rs; jelena.molnar@dh.uns.ac.rs; tamara.apostolovic@dh.uns.ac.rs; srdjan.roncevic@dh.uns.ac.rs; snezana.maletic@dh.uns.ac.rs

Introduction and study objectives

Trifluralin belongs to the di-nitroaniline group of herbicides used in the fight against weeds, which has an aniline structure in its base, and NO₂⁻ functional groups at the 2nd and 6th or 3rd and 5th positions of the benzene ring [1]. It has been used in agriculture since 1963 [2], but since 2007, according to directive 2007/629/EC, the use, import and circulation of trifluralin has been prohibited on the territory of the European Union. One of the main characteristics of trifluralin is its persistence resulting from poor mobility, which can affect crops in the following season in the crop rotation [3]. It is generally known that natural organic matter present in the sediments or soil affects the reduction of the bioavailable fraction of organic pollutants, ie. they affect the sequestration/stabilization of these compounds. This natural sequestration of pollutants in the sediment can be significantly increased by the addition of produced carbon-rich sorption agents [4]. Activated charcoal (AC) is commonly used to protect plants from herbicide damage in soil. The success of AC amendments as a rehabilitation technique for different herbicide residues varies, frequently leading in the herbicide-impacted agricultural area being left alone or alternative crops being planted until the herbicide residues have evaporated. Biochars are relatively novel additions that are also being utilized to reduce possible off-site transfer or for clean-up [5]. The overall goal of this research is to investigate the potential of applying carbon-rich agents, with the aim of local change of geochemical properties of the sediment for the purpose of immobilization and sequestration of selected organic pollutants in the sediment from the aspect of selecting carbon sorption agents (activated carbon and biochar); determining the optimal amount of material; testing the long-term and short-term effects of the addition of these agents on the bioavailability of trifluralin in order to examine the effect of aging and toxicity of the resulting mixtures.

Materials and methods

Characterization of sediment. Sediment was collected from Jegrička River in Autonomous Province of Vojvodina (Republic of Serbia). Sediment was air dried in the dark at room temperature, ground, sieved

and analysed. *Characterization of sorbents.* As expected, activated carbon compared to biochar had the highest value of total organic carbon (83.3%), which reflects the high hydrophobicity and purity of the applied carbon sorbent. On the other hand, the values of total organic carbon for biochar are significantly lower (54.7% for total organic carbon and 81.0% for carbon, respectively) indicating that this applied carbon sorbents are more polar than active carbon. In addition, the specific surface area and porosity of biochar is lower compared to activated charcoal. Thus, activated carbon has the highest specific surface area and porosity, several times higher than the specific surface area and porosity of the examined biochar. T-test showed that there are no micropores in the sample of biochar hale the volume of micropores was 0.18 cm³/g for activated carbon. However, additional evaluations using the HK method showed the presence of micropores in all tested materials. Based on the obtained results, it is concluded that activated carbon has a microporous structure, while biochar consists mainly of mesopores.

Results and Discussion

The evaluation of the efficiency of the added sorption agents on the immobilization of trifluralin was performed based on the total desorbed amount of the compound through multi-stage desorption with XAD-4 resin and the estimation of the bioavailable fraction. The effectiveness of the immobilizations was monitored over a long-time interval for four different equilibration times (0, 14, 30, 90 and 180 days), and the impact of sediment aging with sorption agents on the desorption rate, i.e., the bioavailability of selected compounds, was analysed, which can provide further insight. into the sorption mechanism. The addition of activated carbon and biochar in three different concentrations, as well as the amount of desorbed trifluralin, is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Bioavailable fractions of trifluralin after sediment treatment

The figure shows the bioavailable fractions of trifluralin in the treated sediment. The bioavailable fraction of compounds in the sediment without treatment was 67.1%. However, after treatment, it is observed that in all treated samples the bioavailable fractions of compounds were below 15%. The cause of this phenomenon may be the structure of trifluralin and its functional groups that interact with the surface of sorption agents.

Conclusions

The potential of sediment remediation with the addition of carbonaceous materials was examined from an aspect selection of carbon sorption agents (activated carbon and biochar); determination of optimal quantities of materials; examining the long-term and short-term effects of the addition of these agents on bioavailability of trifluralin to examine the effect of aging and toxicity obtained mixtures. The results of pollutant stabilization in sediment show that: (1) Increasing the dose of all three sorption agents leads to an increase in immobilization efficiency and reduction of the bioavailable fraction of selected organic compounds. Optimal dose of the sorption agent is 1% for activated charcoal and 5% for biochar, whereby the lowest bioavailable fractions of compounds using activated carbon; (2) Aging of the mixture of sediment and sorbents leads to a further decrease in the bioavailable fraction. For activated carbon during the first 90 days after which there is no further change bioavailable fractions. In the case of biochar, after 90 days there is an insignificant increasing the bioavailable fraction, which should be investigated further.

References

- [1] Chen J, Yu Q, Patterson E, Sayer C, Powles S. (2021) Dinitroaniline Herbicide Resistance and Mechanisms in Weeds. *Front Plant Sci.*; 12:634018.
- [2] Wallace, D.R., (2014) Trifluralin in encyclopedia of toxicology. In: Wexler, P. (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of Toxicology*, 3rd ed. Academic Press, Oxford, 388–389.
- [3] Maccario, S.; Lucotte, M.; Moingt, M.; Samson-Brais, É.; Smedbol, É.; Labrecque, M. (2022) Impact of Soil Characteristics and Weed Management Practices on Glyphosate and AMPA Persistence in Field Crops Soils from the St. Lawrence Lowlands (Quebec, Canada). *Agronomy*, 12, 992.
- [4] Abel, S., Nybom, I., Mäenpää, K., Hale, E.S., Cornelissen, G., and Akkanen, J. (2017) Mixing and capping techniques for activated carbon-based sediment remediation - efficiency and adverse Effects for *Lumbriculus variegatus*, *Water Research* 114, 104-112.
- [5] Rittenhouse JL, Rice PJ, Spokas KA, Koskinen WC (2014) Assessing biochar's ability to reduce bioavailability of aminocyclopyrachlor in soils. *Environ Pollut*; 189, 92-7.

Acknowledgments: The authors gratefully acknowledge the support of the Twinning excellence on organic soil amendments effect on nutrient and contaminant dynamics in the subsurface project (TwinSubDyn), HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-02, Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Grant agreement No. 101059546.